

UKBOL Standard Operating Procedure: Dispendix iDOT LT

Version 1, January 2026, Owain Powell

Operation

Switching instrument on

1. Power on the instrument by pushing the ON/OFF switch on the right-hand side of the instrument.
2. Wait until the instrument has completed its self-test and the software is fully loaded
3. When the software has loaded, the main menu will appear
4. Accessing the source disk and inserting a source well and sample plate
5. Press the eject trays at the bottom left of the task bar, this will eject the source disk and the target plate tray.
6. When the source disk has fully rotated out of the instrument, insert a I.DOT mini NG source well into the well frame.
7. The well frame can also be detached and re-attached for easy access.
8. A plate without a seal can be placed into the sample plate tray. For optimal performance, stack target plate adapters underneath the target plate until the top of plate is level with the midpoint of the sloped section of the target plate tray.
9. Press the retract trays or source button to retract the source disk and target plate tray.

Turning off the instrument

1. When turning off the instrument, make sure that the source tray and target plate tray is empty.
2. Press the ON/OFF button, this will show a 5 second countdown, if you accidentally shut it down you can press it again to prevent it from turning off in this 5 second period.
3. After this period the instrument will shut off

Cleaning the instrument

1. Do not flush or spray clean the instrument
2. Clean the screen with a lint free cloth, lint can get into the instrument and block the wells
3. Do not autoclave any part of the instrument
4. Accessing drop detection

GENERAL LAB USERS SHOULD NOT CLEAN THE DROP DETECTION APETURE

Running SCR adapter ligation and SYBR green protocols

Selecting a protocol

1. From the main menu, select dispense on the left-hand column, then select dispense in the centre of the display.
2. Select “start with protocol” and pick the desired protocol from the drop-down menu.

Running a protocol

1. After selecting a protocol, select the plate size required in the tab “Plate Format”
2. Select the Target plate layout using the sliders to the right and beneath the Target plate on the tab called “Target Layout”, liquid classes and volumes should be pre-selected, however may need to be manually selected. This can be done on the drop-down menu for each part. For Splints, the P5 and P7 target layouts may have to be selected separately. To do this select each splint by changing the selected splint in the Liquid drop down menu.
3. Multiple plates can be processed in the same protocol, to do this change to the Number of target plates at the bottom of the tab.
4. Once complete, press next and the Loading Tab will tell you which liquids to load into which source tray well, if you have not put a source well into the Source tray, you can do this now by pressing eject tray or by selecting the source well in the source tray. You can move the trays from position to position on the IDOT by pressing them and dragging them to the desired position.
5. Add all desired liquids into the specific source trays, ensuring you do not touch the hole at the bottom of the wells, or leaving any bubbles or residue on the side of the well.
6. Once step 4 and 5 is completed you can proceed to dispensing.
7. Ensure your target plate is in target plate tray and that all source wells are in the correct position with the minimum volume shown in the Loading tab (it is good practice to add 3-5uL or 5% extra into each well to ensure all wells are dispensed into), and that the target plate is not sealed.
8. Press “Start Dispensing”
9. Once dispensing is completed the tray will open, all wells showing as green have been successfully dispensed into, all shown as yellow have not. You may have to repeat this run for all wells that have not been dispensed into, you can export the experiment information files by selecting the specific experiment in the Experiment tab on the main menu.
10. Once dispensing has been completed make sure to remove all source wells and target plates from the machine before turning off.

iDOT consumable costing

iDOT uses proprietary source tubes, which each cost £8.50. For the adapter ligation we use 4 per plate (£34 per plate or £0.35 per sample). Tips are £4.80 per box and adapter ligation uses 4 boxes per plate (£19.20 per plate or £0.20 per sample). While the cost per sample is greater with iDOT the number of plates processed per day is substantially more and there is a 99.7% reduction in plastic waste. Furthermore, the iDOT enables reaction miniaturization which will offer substantial consumable cost savings in future.